

Dibenzylidenethiocarbohydrazide as a New Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Ruthenium(III)

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Dibenzylidenethiocarbohydrazide (DBTCH) forms two types of coloured complexes with ruthenium(III) under hot condition. One is yellowish brown in the pH range of 5.2-6.5, extractable in chloroform and exhibits maximum absorption at 370 nm. The other is pink in colour formed in the acidity range of 1.0 to 2.5M in hydrochloric acid, soluble in 40% ethanol, partially extractable in organic solvents and exhibits maximum absorption at 530 nm in ethanol. The former obeys Beer's law over the concentration range of 0.5-3.2 ppm and the optimum range of concentration with the highest accuracy as evaluated from Ringbom's curve is 0.7-2.2 ppm. The latter obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 1.0-7.0 ppm and the optimum range of concentration is 1.8-5.0 ppm. Sandell's sensitivity and molar absorptivity values for yellowish brown complex are $0.0031 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and $3.315 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively and for the pink coloured complex the corresponding values are $0.0077 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ and $1.326 \times 10^4 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The reagent permits the determination of ruthenium(III) in acid medium in presence of commonly associated base metals and other platinum metals. In acetate medium, however, some of the base metals and platinum metals interfere.

A number of organic reagents had been recommended for the colorimetric determination of ruthenium(III)¹⁻⁷. Barring a very few⁸ the interferences of the other platinum metals could not be avoided without prior separation. In some other cases⁹ the reagents were not very stable.

The condensation products of thiocarbohydrazide⁹ with different aldehydes yield a series of compounds having the general formula $\text{RCH}=\text{N.NHCSNHCH}=\text{NR}$ which behaved as pentadentate dibasic ligand like dithizone with four coordinating nitrogen atoms and one thiol group.

Attempts had been made to utilise these compounds as sensitive and selective reagents for the colorimetric determination of platinum metals. These compounds were highly stable. In the present communication dibenzylidenethiocarbohydrazide (DBTCH)¹⁰, a condensation product of thiocarbohydrazide and benzaldehyde, had been utilised as a very sensitive and selective reagent for ruthenium(III) by taking the advantage that the reagent formed a pink coloured complex ($\lambda_{\text{max}}=530 \text{ nm}$) with micro amounts of ruthenium(III) in acid medium in presence of other platinum metals.

In acetate medium the reagent also formed a yellowish-brown coloured complex ($\lambda_{\text{max}}=370 \text{ nm}$) with ruthenium(III). Though the reagent in acetate medium was not so selective, it was more sensitive than that in acid medium. Sensitivities might be compared to any of the methods recommended for the determination of ruthenium. The different molar absorptivity values are shown in Table 1 for comparison.

TABLE 1—SENSITIVITIES OF VARIOUS REAGENTS FOR RUTHENIUM

Reagent	Molar absorptivity $\text{l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
DBTCH in acid medium	1.326×10^4
DBTCH in acetate medium	3.315×10^4
Ammonium thiocyanate ¹	5.50×10^3
2,4,6-Tris(2 Pyridyl)-S-Triazine ²	2.40×10^4
2,2',2''-Terpyridine ³	8.30×10^3
Pentyl 4,6-dihydroxy-5-nitrosocotinate ⁴	4.20×10^4
Isonitrosobenzylacetone ⁵	1.02×10^4
Trifluoperazine ⁷	4.285×10^3
<i>o</i> -Hydroxythiobenzylidrazide ⁶	1.375×10^4
2-Pyrroloethiocarboxylhydrazide ¹¹	1.84×10^4

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents :

A Carl-Zeiss VSU 2 spectrophotometer with 1.0 cm matched silica cells was used for absorbance measurements. The pH values of the solutions were measured with a Systronic pH meter type 331.

A stock solution of ruthenium was prepared by dissolving 1.0 gm of the ruthenium(III) chloride (J. M.) in dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was standardised gravimetrically by TSA¹². Solutions for the spectrophotometric determinations were prepared by dilution of the stock solution with distilled water.

The reagent was insoluble in water and only moderately soluble in ethanol. A $4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ reagent solution was prepared in ethanol. All other chemicals and reagents were of analytical grade.

Buffer solution :

A 10% sodium acetate and 3M hydrochloric acid solutions were used to adjust the solution at different pH values.

Recommended procedure for spectrophotometric determination :

Acid medium :

An aliquot containing 25 to 125 μg of the ruthenium(III) was transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask, 2.5 ml of conc. hydrochloric acid and 10-12 ml of the reagent solution were added. It was heated over a boiling waterbath for 5-10 minutes. The solution was cooled to room temperature and more (2-3 ml) alcohol was added to make up any loss due to heating and finally diluted with distilled water to the mark. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 530 nm after one hour against a reagent blank.

Acetate medium :

An aliquot containing known amount of ruthenium (15-75 μg) was transferred to a 100 ml separatory funnel. It was diluted to 20 ml with distilled water and pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.2-6.5. 2-3 ml ethanol and 2 ml of the reagent solution were added and was heated over boiling waterbath for 20-25 minutes. The solution was cooled to room temperature and extracted thrice with 5 ml portion of chloroform and collected in a 25 ml volumetric flask. It was made upto volume, dried and absorbance was measured at 370 nm against the appropriate reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum :

The absorption spectrum of the pink coloured complex and the yellowish-brown coloured complex are shown in Fig. 1. The wavelengths for the maximum absorption of the complexes were 530 nm and 370 nm respectively. The absorption values of the reagent blank were appreciably low at these regions.

Effect of acidity, temperature and the stability of the complexes :

It was found that the optimum range of acidity for pink coloured complex was 1.0 to 2.5M with respect to hydrochloric acid.

The study of the extraction behaviour of yellowish-brown coloured complex showed that quantitative extraction occurred at 5.2 to 6.5 pH.

Fig. 1. Absorbance curves of Ru(III)-DBTCH complexes and the reagent blank.

The optimum time for heating on the boiling waterbath in acid medium was 5-10 minutes after which the complex decomposed. In acetate medium the optimum time of heating was 20-25 minutes. Both the complexes were quite stable and absorbance reading showed no appreciable change even after 24 hours.

Effect of reagent concentration :

In acid medium pink colour developed when the reagent concentration was 15 times in excess of metal ion concentration and attained maximum value when the reagent concentration was 35 times in molar excess.

In the acetate medium maximum colour formation was attained when the metal to reagent ratio exceeded 1 : 6 and the excess reagent had no adverse effect in the absorbance value.

Effect of solvent :

In acid medium a number of non-aqueous organic solvents namely chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, ethylacetate, isobutyl methyl ketone, isoamyl alcohol were tried to extract the pink coloured complex from the aqueous phase. In all cases the extractions were partial.

In acetate medium the results of the extraction of the complex in different solvents are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EXTRACTION OF THE YELLOWISH BROWN COLOURED COMPLEX IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	% Extraction	Extraction coefficient
Chloroform	100.00	<
1,2-Dichloroethane	100.00	<
Ethyl acetate	98.65	73.08
Isobutyl methyl ketone	96.51	27.65
Carbon tetrachloride	42.00	0.72
Benzene	72.44	2.63

Calibration curve, optimum range and photometric error :

Beer's law was obeyed at 530 nm over the concentration range of 1.0-7.0 ppm for the pink coloured complex and at 370 nm over the concentration range of 0.5-3.2 ppm for yellowish brown coloured complex.

The optimum concentration ranges with the highest accuracy as evaluated from Ringbom's¹³ curve were 1.8-5.0 ppm for pink coloured complex and 0.7-2.2 ppm for yellowish-brown coloured complex. The corresponding relative analysis error per one per cent absolute photometric error calculated according to Ayre's¹⁴ equation were 2.720 with 3.5 ppm ruthenium(III) and 2.723 with 1.25 ppm ruthenium(III).

Molar absorptivity of the complex, the sensitivity of the colour reaction are shown in Table 3. The relative mean error and the relative standard deviations obtained from five identical sets of experiments are also indicated.

TABLE 3—CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ANALYTICAL METHODS

Nature of the complex	Molar absorptivity $1 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Sandell's ¹⁵ sensitivity $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$	Relative mean error (%)	Standard deviation (%)	Coefficient of variation (%)
Pink coloured	1.326×10^4	0.0077	0.50	0.38	0.57
Yellowish brown coloured	3.315×10^4	0.0031	0.21	0.28	0.86

Confidence limit :

In acid medium with 67.5 μg of ruthenium, the average of 5 determinations was 67.20 μg which varied between $67.20 \pm 0.36 \mu\text{g}$ at 90% confidence limit.

In acetate medium with 33.1 μg ruthenium the average value varied between $33.17 \pm 0.27 \mu\text{g}$ at 90% confidence limit.

Composition of the complex :

In acid medium the composition of the ruthenium(III)-DBTCH complex could not be ascertained by any of the conventional methods.

In acetate medium the empirical formula of the complex was determined by mole-ratio¹⁶ method and verified by slope-ratio¹⁷ method. It was found to be 1 : 3 (metal : ligand) complex. The overall formation constant ($\log \beta$) of the complex was found to be 15.41.

Effect of diverse ions :

In the study of the effect of diverse ions, the standard ruthenium(III) solution containing known amount of metal was mixed with varying amounts of diverse ions and recommended procedure was followed. The tolerance limits (i.e. concentration of the diverse ions causing an error less than $\pm 2.0\%$ in the transmittance value) are recorded in Table 4.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS IN THE DETERMINATION OF RUTHENIUM(III)

Foreign ion added	Source	Amount tolerated in mg ; [Ru=67.5 μg] [acid medium]	Amount tolerated in mg , [Ru=33.1 μg] ; [acetate medium]
Ti(IV)	Ti(SO ₄) ₂	1.0	1.0 ^b
V(V)	NaVO ₃	1.5	1.0
Cr(III)	Cr ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	1.0	1.0 ^b
Mn(II)	MnSO ₄	1.5	1.5 ^b
Fe(III)	FeCl ₃	1.0 ^{a,d}	1.0 ^b
Co(II)	CoSO ₄	0.95	0.95 ^b
Ni(II)	NiSO ₄	1.0	1.0 ^b
Cu(II)	CuSO ₄	0.75 ^h	nil
Zn(II)	ZnSO ₄	2.5	2.5 ^b
Cd(II)	CdSO ₄	2.5	2.5 ^b
Hg(II)	HgCl ₂	1.0	1.0 ^{b,c}
Pb(II)	Pb(Ac) ₂	1.0	1.0 ^{b,d}
Bi(III)	Bi(NO ₃) ₃	1.0	1.0 ^b
Sb(III)	SbCl ₃	1.0	1.0 ^b
Au(III)	HAuCl ₄	0.75	0.50 ^{e,f}
Mo(VI)	Na ₂ MoO ₄	1.5	1.0
W(VI)	Na ₂ WO ₄	1.5 ^f	1.0
U(VI)	UO ₂ ²⁺ -acetate	1.5	1.0
Os(VI)	OSO ₄ (in NaOH + EtOH)	0.5	0.2 ^g
Pd(II)	PdCl ₂	1.2	nil
Rh(III)	RhCl ₃	1.0	nil
Ir(III)	IrCl ₃	1.25	nil
Pt(IV)	H ₂ PtCl ₆	0.90 ^f	nil
Citrate	Sodium citrate	500	nil
Oxalate	Sodium oxalate	500	100
Tartrate	Sodium-Potassium tartrate	500	100
Phosphate	KH ₂ PO ₄	500	200
Nitrate	KNO ₃	2000	2000
Iodide	KI	2000	200
Bromide	KBr	2000	200
Fluoride	NH ₄ HF ₂	1000	200
EDTA	Sodium-EDTA	500	10

a=in presence of F⁻ ; b=in presence of Ca-EDTA ; c=in presence of I⁻ ; d=in presence of tartrate ; e=prior reduction with oxalic acid ; f=filtered or centrifuged ; g=prior reduction with SO₂ ; h=in presence of EDTA.

Determination of ruthenium in synthetic sample solutions :

Ruthenium(III) was determined in presence of platinum group metals or iron group metals in acid medium and the results were shown in Table 5. The method can also be utilised to determine the ruthenium in ores and alloys having the composition as shown in the synthetic mixtures.

TABLE 5—ESTIMATION OF RUTHENIUM IN DIFFERENT SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Ruthenium present in each mixture = 67.5 μ g

Composition of the synthetic solution	*Ru(III) found in μ g with 90% confidence limit	*Relative mean error (%)
250 μ g Ir(III) + 180 μ g Pt(IV) + 240 μ g Pd(II) + 200 μ g Rh(III) + 150 μ g Os(VI)	67.30 $\pm$ 0.30	0.30
** 200 μ g Co(II) + 200 μ g Ni(II) + 200 μ g Fe(III) + 200 μ g Cr(III) + 200 μ g Mn(II) + 200 μ g Ti(IV)	67.25 $\pm$ 0.30	0.37
*** 200 μ g Co(II) + 200 μ g Ni(II) + 200 μ g Cr(III) + 200 μ g Mn(II) + 200 μ g Cu(II)	67.15 $\pm$ 0.25	0.52
200 μ g Zn(II) + 200 μ g Cd(II) + 200 μ g Hg(II) + 200 μ g Pb(II) + 200 μ g Bi(III)	67.40 $\pm$ 0.19	0.15

* obtained from 5 sets of determinations ;
** in presence of tartrate ;
*** in presence of EDTA.

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